

Smart systems for diagnosis and control of plant diseases and mycotoxins in the framework of One Health

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Human and animal health are closely connected to plant health for at least two main reasons: 1) *food and feed security* (enough food/feed at the right time to feed people and animals), and 2) *food safety* (plant products free from mycotoxins, pesticide residues and human disease contaminants). Many human and animal health problems are caused or worsened by hunger, malnutrition and poor quality of food and feed. One Health perspective can help optimize net benefits from plant protection, realizing food security and nutrition gains while minimizing unintentional negative impacts of plant health practices on people, animals, and ecosystems.

Plant diseases cost the global economy \$220 billion annually, and invasive insects at least \$70 billion. Up to 40% of global crop production is lost and 35 million hectares of forest are affected by pests reducing their carbon sequestration capacity on average by 69%. Additionally, mycotoxins (e.g. aflatoxins) are a huge global food safety concern, especially in light of recent estimates that they contaminate 60–80% of the food produced worldwide. Climate change, globalisation, rising human population densities, and intensified international trade are reshaping the landscape of plant pest distribution, which threatens the natural and managed environment, agricultural and forestry production, ecosystems, and biodiversity in the EU and beyond. In the last decade, the EU has been confronted with several large-scale outbreaks of new plant pests and the unintentional introduction of regulated pests, whose presence affects the intended use of plants with an economically unacceptable impact. It is therefore crucial to minimise and manage plant disease outbreaks and prevent the introduction of quarantine pests to an area. Surveillance and containment measures as well as increased public awareness could help towards that goal while also providing substantial cost reductions and lowering environmental and human health risk.

Our goal is to develop holistic digital smart systems to aid in the early warning and detection of plant diseases together with a response strategy by using modern sensing technology and Artificial Intelligence. A real time pest surveillance system will be developed for plant diseases consisting of three subsystems: 1) early warning systems using novel forecasting models and IoT sensors, 2) pest detection system using drones, satellites, and smartphone applications, and 3) pest response systems providing data-driven recommendations for containment and counteractive measures. Capacity building activities will be developed with a focus on providing training, education, and resources to farmers, agronomists, and other stakeholders involved in crop protection. Policy recommendations based on the data and insights gathered through the early warning, detection, and response system, will be generated to support the EU goals of reducing pesticide use and managing plant pest outbreaks. Finally, the aim is to advance citizen science and encourage crowdsourcing of evidence and data.

The ultimate goal in the framework of One Health is to speed up the adoption of digital smart technologies in agriculture, thus ensuring a sustainable and resilient agricultural industry in the EU. The development of novel monitoring solutions could aid in the reduction of the use and risk of chemical pesticides and hazardous pesticides as part of the EC Farm to Fork and Biodiversity Strategies, targeting a 50% reduction in the use and risks of chemical pesticides and a 50% reduction in the use of more hazardous pesticides.